

1 **The role of spatially-autocorrelated heterogeneous and anisotropic fracture**
2 **roughness on thermal breakthrough of geothermal doublet systems**

3 **Abstract** Rock fractures, as preferential flow channels, play an important role for
4 thermal breakthrough of geothermal doublet systems in enhanced geothermal systems.

5 Therefore, it is important to study the features of heat and mass transfer within
6 fractures to evaluate thermal recovery of enhanced geothermal systems. The
7 heterogeneous and anisotropic roughness of fractures determines the hydraulic
8 aperture and further changes the flow path of the fluid in fractures. In this study, based
9 on the turning bands random field generator from geological field, the spatially
10 autocorrelated random fields for fracture roughness are generated considering varying
11 correlation lengths. Meanwhile, based on the assumption of lower-dimensional
12 fracture element and elastic thin layer, a thermo-hydro-mechanical coupling model
13 covering fracture deformation is proposed considering heterogeneous and anisotropic
14 roughness of fracture. Based on this, the effect of heterogeneous and anisotropic
15 roughness on heat and mass transfer within fracture is analyzed by designing five
16 cases with a total of 182 simulations. Further, the joint effects roughness anisotropy
17 and well layouts on thermal breakthrough and thermal power are investigated. This
18 study can provide the guidance for layout and optimization of geothermal doublet
19 systems in enhanced geothermal system.

20 **Keywords:** thermo-hydro-mechanical coupling, fracture roughness anisotropy,
21 geothermal doublet systems, thermal breakthrough, channeling flow

22 1. Introduction

23 As energy and environmental issues become increasingly prominent, the
24 development and utilization of emerging energy and renewable energy has attracted
25 extensive attention. Renewable energy is a form of energy that can be regenerated in
26 the natural environment, including wind, water, geothermal and solar energy[1]. As a
27 renewable energy, geothermal energy has a large storage and stable output, and has
28 the innate advantage of being almost unaffected by external factors such as climate or
29 season[2]. Therefore, the clean and renewable geothermal energy shows a broad
30 development prospect.

31 Geothermal energy from hot dry rocks has been become an important part of
32 geothermal energy development. Owing to the low permeability of hot dry rocks, the
33 effective permeability of the geothermal reservoir is enhanced using hydraulic
34 fracturing technique before injection of cold fluids, that is, an Enhanced Geothermal
35 System (EGS) is constructed[3, 4]. Geothermal doublet system is a common form of
36 geothermal exploitation and utilization in EGS. Obviously, fractures dominate the
37 fluid flow in geothermal doublet system of EGS. Meanwhile, fractures can also cause
38 short-circuits between injection and production wells, reducing the efficiency of
39 EGS[3]. Additionally, the thermo-hydro-mechanical (THM) coupling process is vital
40 for predicting the performance of geothermal doublet system containing a single
41 fracture or fracture network due to the change of fracture aperture[5-8]. When a single
42 fracture is main fluid pathway for fluid circulation, the heterogeneous or anisotropic

43 fracture roughness may lead to the formation of channeling flow on the fracture
44 surface, which results in the change of thermal breakthrough[9].

45 In recent years, great progress has been made in the study of flow and heat
46 transfer characteristics of rough fractures or discrete fracture networks in EGS. Guo et
47 al.[10] investigated the channeling flow for a single fracture with heterogeneous
48 fracture aperture field in EGS. Liu et al.[11] studied the effect of fracture geometry
49 (i.e. fractal fracture) on thermal breakthrough in geothermal doublet, but the hydraulic
50 aperture is assumed to be homogeneous. Okoroafor et al.[12] analyzed the role of
51 fracture aperture anisotropy on heat transfer based on laboratory-scale fractures. Chen
52 et al.[13] investigated the heat transfer characteristics of rough cracks at the
53 laboratory-scale through numerical simulation. The results show that the changes of
54 convex contact and void space caused by stress changes increase the heterogeneity of
55 streamline distribution and water temperature distribution in artificial fractures.
56 Additionally, Luo et al.[14], Chen et al.[15] and He et al.[16] investigated the impact
57 of fracture roughness on geothermal energy extraction based on 2D discrete fracture
58 network. However, there are few researches on thermal breakthrough considering the
59 spatially-autocorrelated heterogeneous and anisotropic fracture roughness at 3D
60 field-scale. This knowledge gap makes this study of great research significance.

61 Therefore, the purpose of this study is to reveal the effect of the heterogeneity
62 and anisotropy of fracture roughness on thermal breakthrough and thermal power in
63 geothermal doublet system by considering the THM coupling effect. Based on this,

64 the rest of this paper is arranged as follows. First, Section 2 introduces the deduction
 65 and implementation of the multi-physics coupling model, including the generation of
 66 heterogeneous roughness fields. Subsequently, the presented model is verified by two
 67 analytical solutions in Section 3. Third, Section 4 conducts numerical simulation and
 68 result analysis. Finally, the conclusions are drawn in Section 5.

69 2. Coupled THM model considering heterogeneous fracture roughness

70 2.1 Fluid flow equations

71 The saturation pressure flow in the porous matrix can be described by Darcy's
 72 law.

$$73 \quad \mathbf{v}_m = -\frac{k_m}{\mu_w}(\nabla p + \rho_w \mathbf{g}) \quad (1)$$

74 Considering the reservoir rock deformation, the fluid continuity equation can be
 75 expressed as:

$$76 \quad \rho_w S_m \frac{\partial p}{\partial t} - \nabla \cdot (\rho_w \mathbf{v}_m) = -\rho_w \alpha_m \frac{\partial \varepsilon_v}{\partial t} \quad (2)$$

77 The flow process of discontinuities such as faults and fractures contained in
 78 reservoirs can be described by mass conservation equation:

$$79 \quad d_h \rho_w S_f \frac{\partial p}{\partial t} - \nabla \cdot (d_h \rho_w \mathbf{v}_f) = -d_h \rho_w \alpha_f \frac{\partial \varepsilon_{vf}}{\partial t} \quad (3)$$

80 The fluid flow in fractures can be described by Darcy's law in a thin layer of
 81 porous medium:

$$82 \quad \mathbf{v}_f = -\frac{k_f}{\mu_w}(\nabla_T p + \rho_w \mathbf{g}) \quad (4)$$

83 where the subscripts m, f , and w respectively denote rock matrix, fracture and water; p
84 is the fluid pressure; S is the storage coefficient; \mathbf{v} is the Darcy's velocity vector; μ
85 denotes the fluid's dynamic viscosity; k refer to the permeability; d_h denotes the
86 hydraulic aperture of fracture; α is the Biot's coefficient; ρ is the density; ε_v is the
87 volumetric strain; \mathbf{g} is the gravity acceleration vector and ∇_T is the tangential gradient.

88 2.2 Energy conservation equations

89 When the local thermal equilibrium assumption is adopted, the energy
90 conservation equations in porous rock matrix and fractures are respectively expressed
91 as follows:

$$92 \quad (\rho c)_{eff,m} \frac{\partial T}{\partial t} - \nabla \cdot (\kappa_{eff} \nabla T) + \rho_w c_{p,w} \mathbf{v}_m \cdot \nabla T = 0 \quad (5)$$

$$93 \quad d_h \rho_w c_{p,w} \frac{\partial T}{\partial t} - \nabla \cdot (d_h \kappa_w \nabla_T T) + d_h \rho_w c_{p,w} \mathbf{v}_f \cdot \nabla_T T = 0 \quad (6)$$

94 with

$$95 \quad \begin{aligned} (\rho c)_{eff,m} &= (1 - \phi_m) \rho_s c_{p,s} + \phi_m \rho_w c_{p,w} \\ \kappa_{eff,m} &= (1 - \phi_m) \kappa_s + \phi_m \kappa_w \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

96 where T is the temperature; the subscript s denotes the rock skeleton; eff is the
97 abbreviation of effective; c_p is the specific heat capacity; ϕ_m is the porosity of rock
98 matrix; and κ is the thermal conductivity.

99 2.3 Deformation equations

100 2.3.1 Deformation in bedrock

101 The theory of poroelasticity can be used to describe the interaction between fluid,
102 temperature and deformation in geothermal reservoirs. In other words, the relationship

103 among stress, total strain, thermal strain, and pore pressure can be written as

$$104 \quad -\nabla \left[\mathbf{D} : (\boldsymbol{\varepsilon} - \alpha_T (T - T_0) \mathbf{I}) - \alpha_m (p - p_0) \mathbf{I} \right] = \mathbf{F}_v \quad (8)$$

105 where \mathbf{D} is the elastic matrix; p_0 is the reference pore pressure; α_T denotes the
106 thermal expansion coefficient; \mathbf{I} is the identity matrix; T_0 is the reference temperature;
107 \mathbf{F}_v is the body load; $\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}$ is the total strain tensor for infinitesimal deformation, and it is
108 expressed using the displacement vector \mathbf{u} :

$$109 \quad \boldsymbol{\varepsilon} = \frac{1}{2} (\nabla \mathbf{u} + \nabla^T \mathbf{u}) \quad (9)$$

110 2.3.2 Deformation of fracture

111 Owing to the thin structure perpendicular to the fracture plane, the fracture can
112 be treated as a thin elastic layer (TEL) owning independent stiffness. Therefore, the
113 constitutive relation controlling fracture deformation follows the Hooke's law. The
114 total fracture stiffness \mathbf{K} including normal and tangential direction, can be
115 expressed as[11].

$$116 \quad \mathbf{K} = k_n \mathbf{n} \otimes \mathbf{n} + k_s (\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{n} \otimes \mathbf{n}) \quad (10)$$

117 where \mathbf{n} refers to the unit normal vector of the fracture surface; k_n and k_s are
118 respectively the normal and shear stiffnesses.

119 When the TEL thickness d_m (i.e. the mechanical aperture of fracture) is known,
120 the normal and shear stiffnesses are estimated through a state of plane strain[11],

$$121 \quad k_n = \frac{E_f (1 - \nu_f)}{d_m (1 + \nu_f) (1 - 2\nu_f)} \quad (11)$$

122
$$k_s = \frac{G_f}{d_m} = \frac{E_f}{2d_m(1+\nu_f)} \quad (12)$$

123 where E_f , ν_f , and G_f respectively denote the elastic modulus, Poisson's ratio,
 124 and shear modulus of the TEL.

125 Given the deformation of the TEL (fracture) and the relationship between
 126 hydraulic aperture and mechanical aperture (Eq.(20)), the evolution of hydraulic
 127 aperture follows

128
$$\frac{d_h}{d_{h0}} = \left[1 + \varepsilon_f^n(T, p) + (1 + \nu_f)(1 - 2\nu_f) \frac{P - P_0}{E_f(1 - \nu_f)} \right]^2 \quad (13)$$

129 where ε_f^n is the normal strain of TEL depending on the temperature and fluid
 130 pressure.

131 Based on Eq.(13), the fracture permeability is calculated by cubic law.

132
$$k_f = \frac{d_h^2}{12} \quad (14)$$

133 2.4 Heterogeneous and anisotropic fracture toughness field

134 In previous numerical investigations on seepage and heat transfer in fractured
 135 rock mass, fractures were often regarded as parallel plates. In other words, the rough
 136 fracture surface is not considered[16]. The fracture toughness can be described using
 137 Joint Roughness Coefficient (JRC). Luo et al.[14] stated the existence of statistical
 138 distributions of JRC in naturally fractured rock mass at macro-scale by the statistical
 139 analysis of field data in terms of Oskarshamn/Forsmark[17] and Bakhtiary[18]. From
 140 Fig. 1, the JRC distributions of fractured rock mass at macro-scale follow normal and

141 lognormal distribution, respectively. In fact, in the real geological environment, the
 142 mechanical aperture, hydraulic aperture and surface roughness of fractures may
 143 follow spatially autocorrelated random distribution. The spatially autocorrelated
 144 feature can be described by variogram model and correlation length[10, 19]. In
 145 general, the variogram models in geostatistics include exponential, spherical, and
 146 Gaussian models. In terms of correlation length, an intuitive interpretation is that
 147 beyond this distance, the semi-variance does not change remarkably with further
 148 increase in distance[10].

149 In this study, the fracture roughness follows the lognormal distribution from a 2D
 150 turning bands random field generator (TBSIM)[20, 21]. It is an earlier method used in
 151 geostatistics and its simulation efficiency is higher owing to the use of dimensionality
 152 reduction. The turning band method does not directly simulate high-dimensional
 153 random fields, but first independently simulates one-dimensional line processes on
 154 several straight lines in different directions, and then uses the weighted average of the
 155 corresponding simulated values of the line process as the simulated values of the
 156 high-dimensional field. When a random field $\{X(t), t \in \mathbf{R}\}$, with zero mean and
 157 continuous covariance function C_X , and a uniformly distributed random vector \mathbf{U}
 158 over the unit sphere \mathbf{S}_d of \mathbf{R}^d are considered,

$$159 \quad \forall \mathbf{x} \in \mathbf{R}^d, \quad Y(\mathbf{x}) = X(\langle \mathbf{x}, \mathbf{U} \rangle) \quad (15)$$

160 where \langle, \rangle denotes the standard inner product in \mathbf{R}^d .

161 According to Eq.(15), a random field $\{Y(\mathbf{x}), \mathbf{x} \in \mathbf{R}^d\}$ with zero mean and
 162 isotropic covariance C_Y is obtained.

$$163 \quad C_Y(r) = \int_{\mathbf{S}_d} C_X(\langle \mathbf{h}, \mathbf{u} \rangle) \varpi_d \mathbf{d}\mathbf{u} \quad (16)$$

164 where ϖ_d is the uniform distribution over \mathbf{S}_d , and \mathbf{h} is a vector of \mathbf{R}^d with the
 165 modulus r .

166 When spherical coordinates are adopted, Eq.(16) can be inverted as

$$167 \quad C_X(r) = \frac{d}{dr} [r C_Y(r)] \quad (17)$$

168 Eq.(17) controls the covariance C_X related to the given isotropic covariance
 169 C_Y in \mathbf{R}^d . By fitting measured data, multiple available covariance models can be
 170 selected, such as spherical covariance, exponential covariance, and Gaussian
 171 covariance. Owing to the lack of measured data, this study uses an exponential
 172 covariance model to simulate random processes. The exponential covariance model
 173 for 2D anisotropic random field follows as

$$174 \quad C_Y(r) = C \exp\left(-\sqrt{\frac{r^2}{\lambda_x^2} + \frac{r^2}{\lambda_y^2}}\right) \quad (18)$$

175 where C is the sill, λ_x and λ_y are the correlation lengths in \mathbf{R}^2 . Spatial correlation
 176 indicates how parameters at one location impact that at other locations. A shorter
 177 correlation length corresponds to a higher spatial frequency[19].

178 To avoid obtaining a non-ergodic random field, the spreading process of Eq.(15)
 179 has to be repeated N times.

$$180 \quad Y(\mathbf{x}) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{N}} \sum_{i=1}^N X_i(\langle \mathbf{x}, \mathbf{U}_i \rangle) \quad (19)$$

181 In this study, to focus on the heterogeneity and anisotropy of fracture roughness,
 182 the random fields of fracture roughness are generated based on the aforementioned
 183 TBSIM considered different correlation lengths. Then, considering the distribution of
 184 JRC, Barton presented an empirical model for describing the relationship between
 185 hydraulic aperture and mechanical aperture[22].

$$186 \quad d_h = \begin{cases} \frac{d_m^2}{\text{JRC}^{2.5}}, & d_h \leq d_m \\ d_m, & d_h > d_m \end{cases} \quad (20)$$

187 On the assumption that the mechanical apertures of fractures are constant, the
 188 corresponding hydraulic aperture is calculated through Eq.(20). It is noted that the
 189 mechanical aperture of fractures is required to be greater than the hydraulic aperture.
 190

191 Fig. 1 The normal and lognormal distributions of JRC: (a) from the Oskarshamn/Forsmark
 192 data[17], (b) from the Bakhtiary data[18]

193 2.5 Model setup and simulation procedure

194 As depicted in Fig. 2, a geothermal reservoir of $500 \times 500 \times 500 \text{ m}^3$ is established,
 195 which is located below 3000 m and contains a fracture. The spacing between injection
 196 and production wells keeps 200 m. Since the thickness of the fracture is lower than
 197 that of the large-scale model, the fracture is modeled by a low-dimensional element in

198 this study. The obtained heterogeneous hydraulic aperture field is assigned to the
 199 fracture domain by the interpolation function in COMSOL. The calculated domain is
 200 discretized by 329 164 linear tetrahedral elements, in which the mesh is properly
 201 refined by fixed maximum element size of 5 m in 2D fracture zone depicted in Fig. 2.
 202 The constant mass flow rate and pressure boundary conditions are specified at the
 203 intersection of geothermal well and fracture surface to model injection and production.
 204 The producing well is fixed as constant pressure through the Pointwise Constraint.
 205 The injection wells are respectively set to constant pressure and mass flow to model
 206 different injection conditions by Point Mass Source, respectively.

207
 208 Fig. 2 Schematic diagram and model mesh strategy for geothermal doublet system in EGS

209 To better analyze geothermal extraction, the thermal power is calculated as[23]

$$210 \quad W = \rho_w(T) c_w(T) q_{pro}(t) \Delta T \quad (21)$$

211 where q_{pro} is the volumetric flow rates for production well. ΔT is the bottom hole
 212 temperature difference between production and injection wells.

213 3. Model verification

214 3.1 Heat transfer in rock fracture

215 First, the proposed numerical model is verified by the 1D analytical solution from

216 Lauwerier[24]. The domain of $100 \times 100 \text{ m}^2$ is considered and fracture locates in the
 217 middle of model. The related parameters are from the published literatures[11, 25].
 218 The bedrock is assumed to be completely impermeable. The hydraulic aperture of
 219 fracture is fixed as 1 mm, and the fluid velocity in the fracture is maintained at 10^{-2} m/s .
 220 The initial and injection temperatures are set to $80 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ and $30 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, respectively. Fig. 3(a)
 221 and (b) depict the spatial-temporal evolution curves of temperature along the fracture.
 222 As can be seen, the evolutions of temperature are captured fairly well by the proposed
 223 numerical model. Thus, the proposed model is reliable in modeling heat and mass
 224 transfer along fractures.

225

226 Fig. 3 Comparison of spatial-temporal evolution curves of temperature within fracture

227 3.2 THM coupling problem

228 Secondly, the analytical solution from a thermal consolidation problem[5, 16, 26]
 229 is employed to verify the proposed THM coupling model. The analytical solutions to
 230 the pore pressure, temperature, and displacement distributions were presented by Bai
 231 et al.[27]. The geometry model and boundary conditions of thermal consolidation
 232 problem is shown in Fig. 4. The related simulation parameters are listed in Table 1.
 233 Fig. 5 shows the comparison between numerical and analytical results at different

234 heights of the soil column. It can be observed that the numerical solutions are in good
 235 agreement with the analytical solutions, indicating the correctness of the numerical
 236 simulation of the THM coupling process.

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Fig. 4 The geometric model and boundary conditions of thermal consolidation problem

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Table 1 Main input parameters of THM coupled model

Parameters	Values [unit]
Porosity	0.4
Elastic modulus	60 [MPa]
Poisson's ratio	0.4
Soil density	2600 [kg/m ³]
Soil heat capacity	800 [J/kg/K]
Hydraulic conductivity	1×10 ⁻⁹ [m/s]
Total compressibility coefficient	1.1×10 ⁻¹⁰ [Pa ⁻¹]
Biot's coefficient	1.0
Heat conductivity	3 [W/m/K]
Thermal expansion coefficient	3×10 ⁻⁷ [k ⁻¹]
Initial pressure	0.1 [MPa]
Initial temperature	283.15 [K]

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Fig. 5 The evolutions of (a) temperature, (b) pore pressure, and (c) displacement for the thermal consolidation problem

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4. Simulation results and discusses

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To better analyze the simulation results, different simulation schemes are designed, as shown in Table 2. Case #1 mainly analyzes the effect of homogeneous and heterogeneous roughnesses on seepage and heat transfer within fractures. Here, two injection boundaries are considered, namely constant pressure and constant mass flow rate. The effect of fracture roughness anisotropy under two injection boundary conditions is investigated in Case #2 and #3, respectively. Case #4 and #5 discuss the combined effects of different well layouts and fracture roughness anisotropy. The model parameters are listed in Table 3.

254

255 Table 2 Design of simulation cases for geothermal doublet systems

Case		Wellbore layout	Injection boundary	Correlation length (m)	JRC
Case #1	#1-1	Doublet	40 MPa	10, 10	JRC=7.25
	#1-2	Doublet	40 MPa	10, 10	$\ln(\text{JRC}) \sim N(1.9, 0.2)$
	#1-3	Doublet	10 kg/s	10, 10	JRC=7.25
	#1-4	Doublet	10 kg/s	10, 10	$\ln(\text{JRC}) \sim N(1.9, 0.2)$
Case #2	#2-1	Doublet	40 MPa	10, 50	$\ln(\text{JRC}) \sim N(1.9, 0.2)$
	#2-2	Doublet		50, 10	$\ln(\text{JRC}) \sim N(1.9, 0.2)$
	#2-3	Doublet		10, 100	$\ln(\text{JRC}) \sim N(1.9, 0.2)$
	#2-4	Doublet		100, 10	$\ln(\text{JRC}) \sim N(1.9, 0.2)$
Case #3	#3-1	Doublet	10 kg/s	10, 50	$\ln(\text{JRC}) \sim N(1.9, 0.2)$
	#3-2	Doublet		50, 10	$\ln(\text{JRC}) \sim N(1.9, 0.2)$
	#3-3	Doublet		10, 100	$\ln(\text{JRC}) \sim N(1.9, 0.2)$
	#3-4	Doublet		100, 10	$\ln(\text{JRC}) \sim N(1.9, 0.2)$
Case #4	#4-1	Tramline	40 MPa	10, 50	$\ln(\text{JRC}) \sim N(1.9, 0.2)$
	#4-2	Tramline		50, 10	$\ln(\text{JRC}) \sim N(1.9, 0.2)$
	#4-3	Checkboard		10, 50	$\ln(\text{JRC}) \sim N(1.9, 0.2)$
	#4-4	Checkboard		50, 10	$\ln(\text{JRC}) \sim N(1.9, 0.2)$
Case #5	#5-1	Tramline	40 MPa	10, 100	$\ln(\text{JRC}) \sim N(1.9, 0.2)$
	#5-2	Tramline		100, 10	$\ln(\text{JRC}) \sim N(1.9, 0.2)$
	#5-3	Checkboard		10, 100	$\ln(\text{JRC}) \sim N(1.9, 0.2)$
	#5-4	Checkboard		100, 10	$\ln(\text{JRC}) \sim N(1.9, 0.2)$

256

257

258 Table 3 The related simulation parameters

Parameter	E	ν	ρ_s	$c_{p,s}$	λ_s	k_m	ϕ_m	α_T
value	30	0.25	2700	1000	3	1×10^{-18}	0.01	3.5×10^{-6}
unit	GPa	-	kg/m ³	J/kg/K	W/m/K	m ²	-	1/K
Parameter	E_f	ν_f	e_m	ϕ_f	α_m	α_f	S_f	S_m
value	30	0.025	100	1	0.6	1	1×10^{-10}	1×10^{-9}
unit	MPa	-	μm	-	-	-	1/Pa	1/Pa

259 4.1 Effects of heterogeneous fracture roughness

260 The effects of heterogeneous fracture roughness on heat and mass transfer in
261 geothermal doublet systems are investigated in this section. Different heterogeneous
262 roughness distributions are generated by TBSIM, and then the heterogeneous
263 hydraulic aperture distributions are obtained by Eq.(20). The heterogeneity of flow
264 velocity fields in fractured rock mass is mainly caused by the occurrence and
265 distribution of fractures. For single fracture, in addition to the influence of fracture
266 occurrence itself, the heterogeneous roughness of fracture surface can make the
267 fracture itself as the dominant flow channel generate channeling flow to form the
268 secondary dominant flow channel. However, the parallel plate model is used to
269 calculate flow, which ignores the secondary dominant flow channel and thus
270 underestimates or overestimates the risk of thermal breakthrough. To avoid the
271 influence of randomness of fracture roughness distribution hypothesis, 10 realizations
272 for each scenario are generated.

273 Fig. 6 firstly presents the heterogeneous JRC and the hydraulic aperture of
274 Realization 1 when $\lambda_x = \lambda_y = 10$ m. Secondly, the streamline surfaces and temperature
275 distributions are respectively plotted for both homogeneous and heterogeneous
276 roughness. It can be observed that the heterogeneous roughness results in flexural
277 streamline, which in turn affects the heat transfer path. Comparing the streamlines in
278 homogeneous and heterogeneous roughness under constant pressure boundary, the
279 mean flow velocity of former is higher than that of the latter. It can be observed that
280 whether the heterogeneous aperture field results in an effective flow path along the

281 geothermal doublet direction is crucial for thermal breakthrough. In addition, the
 282 constant flow boundary obviously produces higher flow velocity than the constant
 283 pressure boundary, so the thermal convection becomes more significant.

284
 285 Fig. 6 The distributions of flow rate and temperature field for homogeneous and heterogeneous
 286 roughness at $t=1 \times 10^9$ s, where the heterogeneous roughness field is from Realization 1 for $\lambda_x=10$
 287 m and $\lambda_y=10$ m

288 Fig. 7(a) plots the evolution curves of production temperature for Case#1. It can
 289 be observed that under constant injection pressure, the production temperature curve
 290 with heterogeneous roughness is significantly higher than that with homogeneous
 291 roughness. This is due to the heterogeneous roughness field resulting in the
 292 heterogeneity of hydraulic aperture and flow velocity in fractures (Fig. 6). The
 293 fracture zone with higher roughness increases flow impedance remarkably, and the
 294 channeling path increases the effective flow channel length and delays the thermal

295 breakthrough. When the injection boundary is fixed as constant mass flow, the two
296 production temperature curves almost coincide, because the constant flow boundary
297 leads to the gradual increase of injection pressure over time, which reduces the
298 influence of hydraulic fracture heterogeneity on fluid flow velocity. The error bar of
299 the production temperature curve also confirms this.

300 As can be seen from Fig. 7(b), the thermal power rises first and then gradually
301 declines. Similarly, the thermal power curves at the constant injection mass flow
302 almost coincide. Under constant injection pressure, the mean thermal power under
303 heterogeneous roughness is lower than that under homogeneous roughness. Different
304 from the production temperature, the thermal power error bar is larger at the constant
305 flow rate. It is because the thermal power depends not only on the production
306 temperature but also on the outflow rate of production well. The Box-Plot of
307 production temperature for Case#1 at $t=1\times 10^9$ s is plotted in Fig. 8. The production
308 temperature of Case#1-2 is 129°C to 170°C, which is larger than that of the Case#1-4.
309 This indicates that the injection boundary has a great influence on the thermal
310 breakthrough in geothermal doublet system containing fracture with heterogeneous
311 hydraulic aperture. The production temperature of Case#1-1 is smaller than Case#1-2,
312 which means that the homogenous fracture roughness may overestimate the thermal
313 breakthrough.

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Fig. 7 Evolutions of production temperature and thermal power for Case #1

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Fig. 8 Box chart of production temperature for Case#1 at $t=1 \times 10^9$ s.

318 4.2. Effect of fracture roughness anisotropy

319 The anisotropy of fracture roughness may affect the geothermal breakthrough of
320 the geothermal doublet system. As depicted in Fig. 9, the anisotropic roughness fields
321 are generated by setting the correlation lengths of different directions. Case #2 and #3
322 aim to analyze the effect of fracture roughness anisotropy on geothermal recovery
323 under two injection strategies.

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Fig. 9 JRC and hydraulic aperture for anisotropic random fields from Realization 1

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Obviously, in Case#2-1 and Case#2-3, the flow tends to be more perpendicular to

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the geothermal doublet direction, possibly delaying the thermal breakthrough time. In

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Case#2-3 and Case#2-4, the anisotropy of the heterogeneous field is stronger than that

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in Case#2-1 and Case#2-2. Fig. 10(a) shows the thermal breakthrough curves under

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different cases. With the increase in roughness anisotropy, the thermal breakthrough is

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delayed gradually. This is because the connected low-velocity zones form along one

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direction as fracture roughness anisotropy increases, reducing the risk of thermal

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breakthrough. It can be observed from Fig. 10(b) that the thermal powers in Case#2-3

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and #2-4 are biggest and smallest one, respectively. However, the thermal powers in

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Case#2-1 and #2-2 have almost the same evolution pattern in terms of mean values.

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Fig. 10 Evolutions of production temperature and thermal power for Case #2

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Fig. 12 shows the thermal breakthrough and thermal power curves for constant

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flow injection. At this time, the anisotropy has little influence on the thermal

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breakthrough curve. On the other hand, thermal power seems to be more discrete.

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Case 3-3 has the highest mean thermal power, which may be due to its higher

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production flow rate. Fig. 11 and Fig. 13 further show the Box-Plot of the production

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temperature for Case#2 and Case#3 at $t=1\times 10^9$, respectively. Overall, Case#3 is much

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less discrete than case#2. In terms of Case#2-1 and Case#3-1, the production

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temperature ranges from 118 °C to 163 °C in Case#2-1 except for an outlier. However,

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the production temperature ranges from 85 °C to 106 °C in Case#3-1. For the same

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random field, only the injection boundary is changed, and outliers disappeared in

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Case#3-1 and Case#3-2, indicating that the dispersion is reduced. In other words, the

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influence of heterogeneous anisotropic roughness on production temperature can be

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reduced by constant rate injection compared with constant pressure injection.

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Fig. 11 Box chart of production temperature for Case#2 at $t=1 \times 10^9$ s

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Fig. 12 Evolutions of production temperature and thermal power for Case #3

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Fig. 13 Box chart of production temperature for Case#3 at $t=1 \times 10^9$ s

358 4.3. Joint effect of fracture roughness and well layout

359 An efficient well placement and configuration strategy is crucial in geothermal

360 reservoirs, especially for EGS[23]. Different layout of geothermal doublets may lead

361 to mutual interference between wells, thus affecting thermal breakthrough[28]. The
 362 configurations for two geothermal doublets, i.e. tramline configuration and
 363 checkerboard well configuration[28-30] are shown in Fig. 14. Furthermore, the joint
 364 effect of fracture roughness and well layout is investigated.

Fig. 14 Geothermal doublet configurations

365
 366
 367 Fig. 15 shows the final temperature distribution for all simulations in Case#4.
 368 Cases#4-1 and Cases#4-2 correspond to tramline configuration under the principal
 369 direction of anisotropic fracture roughness along vertical and horizontal direction,
 370 respectively. Clearly, the thermal breakthroughs seem easier to achieve when the
 371 geothermal doublets orientation and the principal direction of anisotropic fracture
 372 roughness are the same, because flow channels along the horizontal direction are
 373 easier to form. It should be noted that when $\lambda_x=50$ m and $\lambda_y=10$ m, the temperature
 374 distribution of the Realization 9 is significantly different from the other realizations.
 375 For this purpose, the JRC and hydraulic aperture distribution of this realization is
 376 shown in Fig. 16. As can be seen, the position of the two injection wells on the left are
 377 just in the region of high roughness and low hydraulic aperture, which results in the

378 inability to form a high flow channel between two geothermal doublets. Therefore,
379 effective thermal convection cannot be generated, which significantly delays the
380 thermal breakthrough. However, this also reduces the efficiency of hot water
381 extraction. Therefore, the local fracture permeability of geothermal wells should be
382 considered in the selection of geothermal wells.

383 Fig. 17 plots the evolutions of production temperature and thermal power. Case
384 #4-1 and Case#4-2 correspond to the streamline layout when the principal directions
385 of anisotropy are along vertical and horizontal directions, respectively. The biggest
386 difference between the checkerboard layout and the streamline layout is that the
387 former has the potential to create cross flow, which may speed up thermal
388 breakthrough. Therefore, it can be found from Fig. 17 that the thermal breakthrough
389 curve in Case#4-3 is the lowest one. The thermal power curves imply that case#4-3 is
390 the highest one. As shown in Fig. 18, Case#4-1 has the greatest dispersion and the
391 production temperature varies from 107 °C to 167 °C. It indicates that the dispersion
392 of the model is bigger when the orientation of the streamline configuration is
393 perpendicular to the principal direction of the anisotropy. Because the main flow
394 channel is perpendicular to the orientation of geothermal doublets, and the thermal
395 breakthrough mainly depends on the cross-well flow. For Case#4-2, #4-3, and #4-4,
396 the production temperature is relatively centralized except for the presence of outliers
397 (Fig. 18).

Case #4-1 Realization 1-10

Case #4-2 Realization 1-10

398

Case #4-3 Realization 1-10

Case #4-4 Realization 1-10

399

400

Fig. 15 Temperature profile for Case#4 at $t=1 \times 10^9$ s

401
402

Fig. 16 The distributions JRC and hydraulic aperture for Realization 9 of $\lambda_x=50$ m and $\lambda_y=10$ m

403
404

405

Fig. 17 Evolutions of production temperature and thermal power for Case #4

406

407

Fig. 18 Box chart of production temperature for Case#4 at $t=1 \times 10^9$ s

408

Fig. 19 shows the final temperature distribution for all simulations in Case#5.

409

Compared with Case#4, the main difference is that the fracture roughness has higher

410 anisotropy. From Fig. 20(a), the thermal breakthrough curve in Case#5-2 differs
411 greatly from that in Case#5-1 because the flow channel of the former is more
412 significant in the horizontal direction. However, the difference between Case#5-3 and
413 Case#5-4 seems slight, because the checkerboard layout makes the flow field
414 distribution in the two anisotropic fields similar. The difference of thermal
415 breakthrough curves is mainly based on the generation of random fields. It can be
416 found from Fig. 20(b) that Case#5-1 has the lowest thermal power and the
417 corresponding thermal breakthrough curve is the highest (Fig. 20(a)). As can be seen,
418 the later the thermal breakthrough, the smaller the production flow rate. This may lead
419 to a reduction in thermal power.

Case #5-1 Realization 1-10

Case #5-2 Realization 1-10

420

Case #5-3 Realization 1-10

Case #5-4 Realization 1-10

421

422
423

Fig. 19 Temperature profile for Case#5 at $t=1 \times 10^9$ s

424

Fig. 20 Evolutions of production temperature and thermal power for Case #5

425

Fig. 21 shows the Box-Plot of the production temperature for Case#5 at $t=1 \times 10^9$.

426

The production temperatures of Case#5-1 are 111-170 °C. This is basically consistent

427

with Case#4.1 (Fig. 18). The mean production temperature of Case#5-2 is 116 °C,

428

which is much smaller than the Case#5-1 of 141 °C. The relative ratio is about 22%

429 for the mean production temperature if the tramline configuration is adopted, but the
 430 relative ratio is only about 4% for the mean production temperature if the
 431 checkerboard configuration is adopted.

432

Fig. 21 Box chart of production temperature for Case#5 at $t=1 \times 10^9$ s

433

434 5. Conclusions

435 In this paper, a coupling THM model is proposed for EGS containing a
 436 fracture/fault. The heterogeneous and anisotropic random fields for fracture roughness
 437 are considered. Through numerical analysis, the effect of fracture roughness
 438 anisotropy on thermal breakthrough of geothermal doublet systems is quantitatively
 439 investigated. The primary conclusions are drawn as follows:

- 440 ● The heterogeneous roughness results in the heterogeneous hydraulic aperture
 441 field. It alters the flow path and is easy to forms channeling flow, which
 442 affects the thermal breakthrough of geothermal doublet.
- 443 ● The influence of heterogeneous hydraulic aperture field on fluid flow velocity

444 and thermal breakthrough is more significant for constant injection pressure
445 than constant injection mass flow rate. The reason is that, under the condition
446 of constant injection mass flow, the injection pressure significantly increases
447 with time when the flow impedance is high. Thus, the more pumping power is
448 required.

449 ● In heterogeneous and anisotropic hydraulic aperture field, the orientation of
450 geothermal doublets systems has an important effect on thermal breakthrough
451 owing to preferential channeling flow.

452 ● When the principal direction of anisotropy is perpendicular to the orientation
453 of geothermal doublets, the average thermal breakthrough curve in
454 checkboard configuration is significantly lower than that in tramline
455 configuration, which is due to the occurrence of cross flow.

456 ● For the certain heterogeneous hydraulic aperture field, the optimization of
457 geothermal doublets needs to consider many factors, such as injection well
458 boundary, the permeability around the injection well, the anisotropy of the
459 heterogeneous field and well spacing, etc.

460

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